

Application of Framing Theory in Public Relations: An Analysis on Rhetorical Perspective

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Preprint. Version: v1.0, April 03, 2025.

Presented at the Central State Communication Association, 2025.

Abstract

This study seeks to identify drawbacks in framing theory from the perspective of public relations and rhetoric. To explore, this paper resorted to rhetorical theories and tools to make the theory more effective with an intent to contribute to the broader field of public relations and practices. Framing theory is a widely used approach for public relations practitioners in designing successful strategies for public relations endeavors. In other words, framing theory provides a skeleton about how information is shaped and presented before audiences. Although public relations practitioners heavily rely on the theory, one of the pitfalls of the theory is that its use raises important dilemmas about ethical bias for PR practitioners. As a remedy, I draw upon Robert L. Scott's three ethical guidelines—*Toleration, Will, & Responsibility*—derived from the claim that "*Rhetoric is Epistemic*" as a means to address this gap in framing theory.

Keywords: framing theory, public relations, rhetoric as epistemic

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Framing theory in the study of public relations is utilized to disseminate messages and information to the audiences. Over the past few decades, framing theory has been pragmatic and popular in mass communication, especially in public relations (Scheufele, 2004). Besides, the application of framing theory in public relations helps a better understanding of the theory's advancement, while aiding media and publicists to have information in a sophisticated way (Kuan et al., 2021). In general, framing in public relations is about how information is crafted to shape people's perceptions in a nuanced and strategic way.

Despite having multiple applications and significant uses of framing theory in public relations, there is still a risk that exists in framing theory that is often overlooked in ethical issues. Researchers like (Gray et al., 2015) employed an international approach to framing which focuses on how the meanings of framing are consistently compromised among various actors, while increasing scholarship considering this perspective is interpreted in different framing dynamics of ethical issues (Allain, 2012). It indicates that framing in a global perspective involves the interventions of meanings among other groups, with the ongoing scholarly focus on how framing forces impact the interpretation of ethical issues. In its nature, the analysis of public relations includes various standpoints that need to be addressed and analyzed from both critical and rhetorical perspectives.

Public relations can be analyzed from various viewpoints, including a variety of systems, critical analysis, and rhetorical perspectives (Toth, 1992). The rhetorical approach in public relations is engaged with creating messages to provide information between the audience and the organizations. Rhetorical theory encompasses various tools, concepts, and techniques including

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dramatism, syllogism, dialectic, metaphors, analogies, similes, parallelism, ethos, pathos, and logos which create a meaning-making process. According to Borchers & Hundley (2018), these tools, concepts, and techniques allow theorists to discuss the effectiveness of rhetoric, emphasizing the implications of how rhetoric is and how it functions. The premise of the paper is that framing theory has potential contributions and consequences for public relations practices, but it also delves into addressing the consequential lapses in theoretical aspects. One lapse in particular is ethical dilemmas.

This study begins with defining framing theory and its application in communication studies, particularly in public relations. Then it proceeds to identify the theory's ethical issues (e.g., framing bias, manipulation & deception) while applying Scott's (1967) three ethical guidelines (*Tolerance, Will & Responsibility*) to bridge the gap. Finally, it modifies the theory and suggests some guidelines for public relations professionals.

Literature Review

Framing Theory in Communication Studies

The study of framing theory in communication studies has been of great interest recently, gaining wide acceptance and significant media exposure. According to Ardèvol-Abreu (2015), framing theory has been in development since the mid-1960s, when it was first introduced in the field of sociology, allowing a comprehensive way of studying media and its effects on individuals and audiences. First, in this sociological context, Irving Goffman (1974) was one of the leading scholars who developed the concept of framing. According to Goffman, such frames include the "schemata of interpretation," which helps to define a meaningless event and idea into something meaningful (p. 21). This concept plays a crucial role in defining various aspects

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of framing to transfer things into meaning. Thus, framing theory changed significantly over time. According to Appelman & Asmara (2018), although framing theory first emerged in psychology, and was developed in sociology, it finally thrived in the study of communication. One reason for this thriving is because the entire study of framing theory now inherently depends upon communication. Thus, framing theory succeeds in its integral connection to communication while the next section will conceptualize how this theory plays a significant role in communication studies defining problems, finding causes and suggesting remedies.

The process of framing is how various elements of a situation make a meaningful context to identify the problems and make solutions. One of the most productive researchers in framing theory, the American Robert Entman (1993), defined framing as a process into how various aspects and process are considered to make them meaningful, emphasizing the importance to identify the issues which finds proper solutions and actions. He provided some guidelines for how solutions are made by applying framing. He said,

Frames, then, define problems-determine what a causal agent is doing with what costs and benefits, usually measured in terms of common cultural values; diagnose causes identify the forces creating the problem; make moral judgments-evaluate causal agents and their effects; and suggest remedies-offer and justify treatments for the problems and predict their likely effects (p. 52).

This statement reflects how frames work to diagnose problems and propose solutions assuming the probable outcomes. The above discussion proves that framing theory has a crucial role in communication studies which has taken position overnight over agenda-setting theory, achieving people's attention.

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To understand framing theory and how it frames, the notion of framing needs to be defined further in terms of how framing can be used to study media content. De Vreese (2005) claims that the concept of framing understands communication as a dynamic and interactive process. Entman (1993) observed that frames surround the communicators, the messages itself, the recipients, and the broader cultural aspects. These concepts play essential roles in the process of framing to make it more interactive and applicable.

According to Arowolo (2017), framing theory is something that is presented before audiences called “the frame” that influences the choices and concepts of people in how to situate or structure message meaning. So, the framing has a great effect on people’s choices and the structures of messages. Braun (2014) addressed public relations as the deliberate and strategic participation of people in shaping social meanings of a predetermined event or objective. Public relations practitioners must define the meaning of a particular event. From a rhetorical perspective, it is important to discuss and focus on how a message is created and conveyed in making and creating meaning. Hallahan (1999) said,

In addition to a rhetorical approach that focuses on how messages are created, framing is conceptually connected to the underlying psychological processes that people use to examine information, to make judgments, and to draw inferences about the world around them. (p. 206).

Framing in public relations not only discusses crafting messages but also considers the psychological process on how information is interpreted to form opinions. This also employs effective framing in public relations required to understand how people perceive and process information.

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Application of Framing Theory in Public Relations

The application of framing theory in public relations is often reflected in the mass media by framing various content while presenting and addressing meaningful messages to the audiences. Sometimes, the public discourse is usually controlled by a single speaker addressing the public through framing. Sproule (2002) pointed out that those who control mass media including public relations practitioners are influential rhetorically as to what Quintilian once called “the good man speaking well.” According to Sproule’s observation, public relations experts hold rhetorical power to shape public discourse as is reflected in Quintilian’s statement. The Quintilian statement further justifies and follows as Davis (2002) mentions that public relations recently emphasize having community engagement and discourse, considering its significance leading toward a higher level. The phrase attributed by Quintilian encapsulates not only mastering rhetorical skills but also considering characteristics like honesty, and integrity. Quintilian concept of a “good man speaking well.” It underscores that effective persuasion in communication not only depends on rhetorical prowess but also on the ethical credibility of the speaker.

Thus, the appeal of rhetorical skills and ethical credibility denotes the growing importance of public relations practitioners in not only influencing public perceptions but also promoting community engagements. In the article “Seven Models of Framing: Implications for Public Relations.”, Kirk Hallahan (1999) emphasized applying framing in the media on the different perspectives in public relations. Hallahan considered framing in public relations stating that “if public relations is seen as the practice of fostering mutual relationships between various organizations and the public to whom it relies on (Cutlip, Center, & Broom, 1995), then framing

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establishes common interests for cultivating successful relationships” (Hallahan, 2007). So, framing is vital and is unique in all successful public relations campaigns.

One of those campaigns is strategic communications. In public relations practices, framing is used frequently in strategic communications, to influence audiences to see framing from a specific standpoint. According to Allardyce & Diamond (2020), framing can be applied in all forms of communication while utilizing public relations to lurch the viewpoints of the audiences and the targeted groups towards the products, services, and celebrities. Public relations frame the product and services of the organization and work on setting personal ways too.

In addition to framing the product and services of the organization, framing also helps PR practitioners manage issues by framing them so that they can align with organizational goals in achieving outcomes. First, public relations professionals use framing theory to construct messages in a way that can shape public opinion and perceptions. For these reasons, framing has been a great concept for public relations research and practices. (Lim & Jones, 2010; Zoch & Molleda, 2006). Therefore, framing theory guides PR practitioners in how they interact with media, building relationships with journalists so that they can potentially influence media people to frame information in shaping and changing narratives in their direction. Sometimes, PR strategies help to build even better relationships with the journalists, while PR personnel work like a mouthpiece who tells an organization's good news only. In the organization, the frame is seen as a central idea and concept that addresses the meaning of an organization to the events related to the story and an issue (Gamson & Modigliani, 1987). From the media perspective, framing also allows journalists to work with a large amount of information so that it can fit with the issue and incidents. In doing so, framing helps PR professionals to create a vibrant relationship with the media.

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In addition to strategic messaging campaigns and cultivating a relationship with journalists, framing theory is also extremely important during periods of crisis. The role of framing during a crisis has an immense impact on retaining organizational reputation. During any unwanted situation, PR practitioners can strategically frame a crisis to minimize reputational damage and losses. Considering the probable crisis that can happen at the time, PR personnel must be prepared to face the crisis and “to address the underlying issues behind the crisis (issue framing) as well as the cause and potential explanations of responsibility (responsibility framing)” (Hallahan, K. 1999, p. 229). Therefore, crisis management is an integral part of public relations where framing plays a crucial role in measuring and understanding the crisis.

In summary, framing theory plays a critical role in crisis management by helping PR practitioners shape the narrative around a crisis. Through strategic issue and responsibility framing, organizations can mitigate reputational damage, address underlying issues, and explain the causes and accountability related to the crisis. Effective crisis management, therefore, relies heavily on the appropriate use of framing to retain public trust and minimize losses.

Moving forward, the discussion will explore Identifying Areas of Improvement for Framing Theory with a focus on Ethical Considerations. This section will delve into how framing practices can be refined to better address ethical challenges in PR, ensuring transparency and responsibility during crisis communication.

Identifying Areas of Improvement for Framing Theory (Ethical Considerations)

Framing theory has many uses for PR practitioners, the ethical considerations of framing theory require great attention because there are various reasons for securing the credibility of the information in the news releases issued by public relations practitioners. According to Jakopović

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& Skoko (2009), PR experts use various languages and follow the journalistic structure to draft a press release, that includes the “five W’s” questions: who, what where, when, and why. Due to the structure of a media release and press release, a frame contains various segments of information and stories that demand ethical considerations. Because each part of the story has different types of understanding and messages.

In recent times, scholars have begun to more deeply consider the ethical complexities within public relations. Bowen (2007a) claimed that “public relations is a field fraught with ethical dilemmas” (p. 65). It is reported that “in the field of public relations, unethical practices have been regarded as a serious problem with numerous deleterious effects” (Ki et al., 2011, p. 267). This statement underscores the absence of ethical consideration in public relations practices which often creates a situation that slowly tarnishes the image, reputation, and professionalism in the field. unethical issues may arise when PR experts encounter a conflict of interests while promoting a message that they do not find ethically right which has also the potential to harm the public. In these circumstances, PR practitioners may be guilty of manipulation and bias.

To the extent that Manipulation and bias are salient ethical issues in PR practice more broadly, and to the extent that framing is an important tool for PR practitioners, then we can expect that issues of manipulation and bias might also be reflected in framing theory. One example of ethical framing is found in the intersection between PR and presidential campaigns. In presidential campaigns, this bias usually takes on the terms of political orientation and party affiliation (D’Alessio & Allen, 2000; Niven, 2002; but cf. Jamieson & Waldman, 2002; Kuypers, 2002). The manipulation of information and deception is created through political propaganda to one party over another. From political campaigns to announcing the party’s agenda to the media,

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they prefer press releases as one of the best communication tools to reach media and other social networking sites. In most cases, PR persons are assigned to write the press release to disseminate the party's agenda. According to Gilpin (2008), over the years, public relations experts have been considering press releases and news releases to communicate with audiences through various media, while press releases serve as autobiographical narratives through various organizations to convey and manage their identity. Thus, there is a high possibility of circulating misinformation if ethical guidelines are not followed genuinely.

In addition to the above information manipulation biases, ethical deception in framing also happens when the selective presentation of information is considered to evoke certain responses and attitudes. With the rise of social media and Artificial Intelligence (AI), selective framing is becoming a burning issue as it plays a critical role in amplifying a narrative to neglect others. For example, it also spreads misinformation while creating biases. Since a PR person is mainly responsible for circulating news and framing events as a spokesperson on behalf of an organization, there always be a way of circulating selective information to media that questions the credibility of information.

A third ethical dilemma is the transparency of information. Transparency has emerged as one the important concepts in both academics and industry across various disciplines and fields like business, marketing, advertising, public relations, and organizational communication. (e.g., Coombs & Holladay, 2013; Edelman, 2016; Holland et al., 2018; Lee & Boynton, 2017; Rawlins, 2008; Reichardt, 2003). However, sometimes, ethical considerations are overlooked in framing thereby undermining transparency in the information disseminated by PR professionals and concerned personnel of the organizations. For example, when an organization fails to follow framing techniques, it leads them to undermine the ethics of communication. Securing

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transparency to disseminate information in framing has an immense impact on communication practices and research.

Thus, the ethical considerations in framing theory have been overlooked in various ways. In an article on “Ethical Challenges of Framing in Persuasive Communication, in Words and Pictures” Geise & Coleman (2015) termed frame as a process of introducing an idea, concept, message, and news in a way by presenting a particular aspect of the event while framing to induce persuasiveness and credibility in communication. The ethical ground and perspective are the most necessary tool that often disregards framing theory and give importance to studying communication and public relations research and practices.

Theoretical Impulses

To address the probable gap of manipulation and deception in framing theory, I draw upon Robert L. Scott’s three ethical guidelines—*Toleration, Will, & Responsibility*—derived from the claim that “*Rhetoric is Epistemic*” as a means to address this gap in framing theory. In this article, he argues that there are three ethical guidelines that logically follow, namely; toleration, will, and responsibility.

Toleration in rhetoric discusses various perspectives and arguments to create a level of acceptance of different discourses and viewpoints. He encourages recognizing multiple contexts and prospects if they contradict one’s own beliefs. Scott opined that “as a matter of fact, if one can be certain, tolerating deviations from the demands of certainty may itself be deemed evil. On the other hand, uncertainty, taking truth as a toehold to climb into the yet-to-be-created rather than as a program to unfold regardless of the circumstances, demands toleration” (p. 16). So, the

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toleration of rhetoric urges individuals to be open-minded and willing to compromise on various standpoints before disregarding them.

Will is the second ethical guideline. This ethical perspective denotes a constant effort taken by rhetoricians to be more engaged in the matter to think critically and persuasively. Scott defined this as “Inaction, failure to take on the burden of participating in the development of contingent truth, ought to be considered ethical failure” (p. 16). Ethical failure occurred when a rhetorician could not actively participate in disseminating messages through a constructive and meaningful way.

Lastly, responsibility. As an ethical guidelines in rhetoric, responsibility teaches us to use our rhetorical skills morally and responsibly. Moral consideration in rhetoric discusses honesty, integrity, and truthfulness while respecting others' rights and dignity. Scott addresses responsibilities “with intentions for good consequences, but to accept the responsibility for all the consequences in so far as they can be known is part of what being ethical must mean” (p. 17). It underscores an intention for good consequences in rhetoric, welcoming responsibility to diverse situations to broader ramifications, and underlining an ethical decision-making ground for ensuring accountability.

With these guidelines in mind, let us consider how they address the present ethical dilemmas in framing theory. At present, framing theory encounters many ethical dilemmas and concerns including manipulation, bias, and selective presentation of information which creates a lack of transparency in the framing theory. These ethical lapses could impact people's perceptions, trust, and credibility create challenges, and could potentially threaten public relations professionals and practitioners. To address these potential challenges in the PR

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profession, Scott's three ethical guidelines; toleration, will, and responsibility could mitigate the problem and modify the framing theory to be ethically grounded.

Toleration. Let us start with toleration. From a communication perspective, tolerance has great importance in various perspectives to promote different discourses and viewpoints. It teaches us to accept various contexts and comments while recognizing everyone's beliefs and ideas. Considering the job nature of public relations as a diversified field in communication, tolerance helps and encourages us to accept multiple contexts and prospects although it contradicts with own beliefs. Active listening is a central process for PR practitioners as it helps them to culturally informed and transparent conversations with the public and audiences (Place et al., 2023). It underscores the inclusiveness and responsiveness of PR practitioners in communicating from different perspectives with the concerned public. In other words, toleration refers to accepting diverse perspectives and creating an openness to engage with standpoints that differ from each other. It justifies the to seek the pursuit of knowledge and understanding. Considering the diverse nature of the job and responsibility, a PR person must be diversified and respectful of others' viewpoints. Thus, PR experts could benefit from how the way toleration would PR practitioners use framing theory.

Will. Discussing will, Scott says "If one cannot be certain . . . one must either withdraw from the conflicts of life or find some way to act in the face of these conflicts (p. 16)." Will underscores the need to engage with the uncertainties of life and find a way to make decisions even when facing ambiguity. In other words, Scott's statement teaches us to follow resilience and adaptability in facing life challenges. In public relations, engaging in meaningful dialogue and persuasion are essential to reach the goals if they sometimes become uncertain. It helps PR practitioners to be more engaged in thinking critically and actively. According to Stoker &

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Tusinski (2006), PR is such a profession and area of study which often criticizes to negative situations as positive and positive to favorable by adopting and embracing dialogues, prioritizing equality, consensus, and mutual benefit. Discussing the importance of persuasion in PR, Guth & March (2016) said that PR is about “persuasion, information dissemination, or propaganda” (p. 8). Scott suggests that humans do not avoid practicing their will in some cases, while he opines those actions are not consciously willed. It means that sometimes individuals engage in actions or activities without choosing to do so. Thus, PR persons sometimes do not know how and in what capacity they need to engage in the tasks.

Responsibility. Lastly, the third ethical guideline of Scott’s “Rhetoric is Epistemic” is responsibility. PR practitioners must have a moral responsibility to apply their rhetorical skills as it entails being mindful of words and arguments. As Scott says, “Truth is dual: both the precepts I adhere to as well as the situation's demands and potentialities are involved. Responsibility is then also dual: I select the precepts yet act within the given situation (p. 17).” He compares responsibility with truth, considering its dual nature that highlights dynamic relationships between personal beliefs and external circumstances in defining both truth and responsibility. Scott’s ethical consideration of responsibility suggests that a person should have knowledge and practice in their respective activities and the probable results that they produce. The statement also underscores the interconnectedness between ethical behavior and informed decision-making. Thus, the relationship between ethical behavior and informed decision-making is vital for effective PR practices as this strategy helps to build stakeholder relationships, mitigate the crisis, and create good perception to individuals which contributes the overall reputation for the organizations. So, the third ethical instruction of Scott’s “Rhetoric as Epistemic” discusses core

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points of responsibility that are highly relevant for PR professionals to follow and implement in their practices.

Modification of Framing Theory: Ethical Foundations in Public Relations

Scott's three ethical guidelines in "Rhetoric as Epistemic" has the potential to make framing theory more ethically grounded. This study also pointed out how much ethical issues are important in the study and practicing of public relations. Hence, this study suggests the following concepts that could be considered to modify the framing theory to be ethically grounded in applying and implementing PR practices in the study of communication and media studies.

Unification of Ethical Principles

To modify framing theory, the integration of ethical principles could be a remedy for PR practitioners. Considering the multifaceted activities of PR professionals, they must consider ethical issues avoiding manipulation, and selective presentation of information in framing contents to further avert biasness and deception. This strategy also helps to teach PR practitioners to respect diverse perspectives when they frame and construct anything to disseminate their messages and information. This ethical aspect is also reflected in Scott's ethical guideline on responsibility.

Practicing Rhetorical Persuasion

Persuasion is an important aspect of PR for various reasons because PR is a kind of profession that requires the persuader to attract customers to products and services through verbal and non-verbal persuasion. To the extent that persuasion relies upon rhetorical theories, then Scott's ethical guidelines are a natural choice because rhetorical persuasion is highly reflected in Scott's ethical guidelines. PR and rhetoric have a shared meaning in strategic

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advocacy, learning about ethics, virtue, and values to make them relevant and interconnected for the full functioning of society (Heath & Ihlen, 2018). It underscores that ensuring rhetorical persuasion in framing theory for PR works and practices is vital, addressing rhetorical skills like honesty, integrity, and respect for the targeted groups, audiences, and the public.

Applying ethical decision-making frameworks

The application of the moral decision-making process could be considered in framing theory so that PR practitioners diagnose ethical dilemmas. Bowen (2007a) quoted from the International Association of Business Communicators (IABC; 2006) ethics study, suggested that around 70% of public relations practitioners are not prepared to encounter ethical dilemmas due to a lack of ethical training and education. Given the increased importance of evaluation in public relations, ethical dilemmas in decision-making processes should be offered in framing theory.

Addressing Ethical Dialogue and Engagement

Modifying framing theory on emphasizing dialogue and engagement with stakeholders and targeted audiences could be an ideal suggestion. It encourages to focus on implementing active listening while engaging in fruitful conversations. Currently, the business world introduced dialogue as a model of effective ethical communication.

In recent years, the business world has embraced dialogue as the role model for effective, ethical communication. In certain quarters dialogue has attained something of a holy status. It is held up as the summit of human encounter, the essence of liberal education, and the medium of participatory democracy. By virtue of its reciprocity and interaction,

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dialogue is taken as superior to the one-way communiqués of mass media and mass culture. (Peters, 1999, p. 33).

Thus, PR persons should be active in listening to others to get feedback to promote understanding and collaboration. Scott's Rhetoric as Epistemic also discusses the issue of active listening in toleration in his three ethical guidelines.

Discussion and Conclusion

The research sought to introduce framing theory and its significant development and consideration of employing in communication studies. This paper also delved into identifying the role and application of framing theory in public relations. To mitigate and bridge the gap Scott's three ethical guidelines delved from the concept of "*Rhetoric and Epistemic*" has been discussed elaborately and applied to offer some probable advice and guidance for public relations professionals. It is found that these modifications on ethical foundations could potentially help public relations PR actioners to follow and impose ethical issues in their jobs and practice. Public relations practitioners are playing tremendous roles in designating their messages to the public and targeted audiences through various forms of media tools. Besides, the necessity of following the ethical perspective in their work can secure and serve the noble purpose of this profession.

References

- Appelman, A., & Asmara, M. (2018). A crisis by any other name? Examining the effects of journalistic “crisis labeling” on corporate perceptions. *Newspaper Research Journal*, 39(1), 83-92.
- Allain, J. (Ed.). (2012). *The legal understanding of slavery: From the historical to the contemporary*. OUP Oxford.
- Arowolo, S. O. (2017). Understanding framing theory. *Mass Communication Theory*, 3(6), 4.
- Allardyce, N. & Diamond, K. (2020, February 10). “*Theory of Framing*”. Retrieved from <https://sites.psu.edu/nickdyce/2020/02/10/theory-of-framing/>
- Ardèvol-Abreu, A. (2015). Framing theory in communication research. Origins, development and current situation in Spain. *Revista latina de comunicación social*, (70).
- Braun, S. (2015). Can we all agree? Building the case for symbolic interactionism as the theoretical origins of public relations. *Journal of Professional Communication*, 4(1).
- Bowen, S. A. (2007a). Ethics and public relations. Retrieved from <http://www.instituteforpr.org/ethics-and-publicrelations/>
- Borchers, T., & Hundley, H. (2018). *Rhetorical theory: An introduction*. Waveland Press.
- Bowen, S. A. (2007b). *Ethics and public relations*. Gainesville, FL: Institute for Public Relations.
- Coombs, W. T., & Holladay, S. J. (2013). *It's not just PR: Public relations in society*. John Wiley & Sons.

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- De Vreese, C. H. (2005). News framing: Theory and typology. *Information design journal+ document design*, 13(1), 51-62.
- Davis, A. (2002). *Public relations democracy: Politics, public relations and the mass media in Britain*. Manchester University Press.
- D'Alessio, D., & Allen, M. (2000). Media bias in presidential elections: A meta-analysis. *Journal of communication*, 50(4), 133-156.
- Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of communication*, 43(4), 51-58.
- Edelman Public Relations. (2007). 2007 Annual Edelman Trust Barometer. Chicago: Author.
- Edelman, D. J. (1992). Ethical behavior is key to field's future. *The Public Relations Journal*, 48(11), 32.
- Gilpin, D. R. (2008). Narrating the organizational self: Reframing the role of the news release. *Public Relations Review*, 34(1), 9-18.
- Geise, S., & Coleman, R. (2015). Ethical challenges of framing in persuasive communication, in words and pictures. In *Persuasion ethics today* (pp. 199-221). Routledge.
- Goffman, E. (1974). *Frame analysis: An essay on the organization of experience*. Harvard University Press.
- Gray, B., Purdy, J. M., & Ansari, S. (2015). From interactions to institutions: Microprocesses of framing and mechanisms for the structuring of institutional fields. *Academy of management review*, 40(1), 115-143.
- Gamson, W. A., & Modigliani, A. (1987). The changing culture of affirmative action. *Research in political sociology*, 3(1), 137-177.
- Guth, D. W., & Marsh, C. (2016). *Public relations: A values-driven approach*. Pearson.

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- Heath, R. L., & Ihlen, Ø. (2018). Public relations and rhetoric: Conflict and concurrence. *The handbook of organizational rhetoric and communication*, 51-66.
- Holland, D., Krause, A., Provencher, J., & Seltzer, T. (2018). Transparency tested: The influence of message features on public perceptions of organizational transparency. *Public Relations Review*, 44(2), 256-264.
- Hallahan, K. (1999). Seven models of framing: Implications for public relations. *Journal of public relations research*, 11(3), 205-242.
- Jakopović, H., & Skoko, B. (2009). Implementing Framing in Public Relations: Reporting on Climate Change as an Example. *Reconciling the Traditional and Contemporary*, 123.
- Kuypers, J. A. (2002). *Press bias and politics: How the media frame controversial issues*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA.
- Ki, E. J., Choi, H. L., & Lee, J. (2012). Does ethics statement of a public relations firm make a difference? Yes it does!!. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 105, 267-276.
- Kuan, D., Hasan, N. A. M., Zawawi, J. W. M., & Abdullah, Z. (2021). Framing theory application in public relations: The lack of dynamic framing analysis in competitive context. *Media Watch*, 12(2), 333-351.
- Lim, J., & Jones, L. (2010). A baseline summary of framing research in public relations from 1990 to 2009. *Public Relations Review*, 36(3), 292-297.
- Lee, T. H., & Boynton, L. A. (2017). Conceptualizing transparency: Propositions for the integration of situational factors and stakeholders' perspectives. *Public Relations Inquiry*, 6(3), 233-251.
- Niven, D. (2002). *Tilt? The search for media bias*. New York: Praeger.

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Peters, J. D. (1999). *Speaking into the Air: A History of the Idea of Communication*. University of Chicago Press.

Place, K. R., Madden, S., & Pevak, M. (2023). Exploring trauma-informed listening among public relations professionals. *Public Relations Review*, 49(5), 102393.

Rawlins, B. R. (2008). Measuring the relationship between organizational transparency and employee trust.

Reichardt, J. D. (2003). Restoring trust in a 'Joe Millionaire' world. *The Strategist*, 6-10.

Stoker, K. L., & Tusinski, K. A. (2006). Reconsidering public relations' infatuation with dialogue: Why engagement and reconciliation can be more ethical than symmetry and reciprocity. *Journal of Mass Media Ethics*, 21(2-3), 156-176.

Scheufele, B. (2004). Framing-effects approach: A theoretical and methodological critique.

Sproule, J. M. (1988). The new managerial rhetoric and the old criticism. *Quarterly Journal of Speech*, 74(4), 468-486.

Scott, R. L. (1967). On viewing rhetoric as epistemic. *Communication Studies*, 18(1), 9-17.

Toth, E. L. (1992). The case for pluralistic studies of public relations: Rhetorical, critical, and systems perspectives. *Rhetorical and critical approaches to public relations II*, 3-16.